

Philosophy of Education: The Challenges of Globalization and Innovation in the Information Society

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Abstract—Information society is an absolutely new public formation at which the infrastructure and the social relations correspond to the socialized essence of «information genotype» mankind. Information society is a natural social environment which allows the person to open completely the information nature, to use intelligence for joint creation with other people of new information on the basis of knowledge earlier saved up by previous generations.

Keywords—Information society, Philosophy, Education, Globalization and innovation.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN today's rapidly changing world, when the eyes of several generations at the same time there is a change and transformation of socio-cultural and civilizational foundations of human existence, value system, ideology and worldview, it becomes especially important issue of cultural adaptation and socialization strategies. In the social transformation of society and its transition to the new conditions of civilization development is very significant is the problem of choosing a new policy of entering the post-industrial society in his new stage of development, when combined with new technologies are generated and implemented in the social life of innovation and knowledge-intensive products infrastructure. In turn, they are the forces that cause a fundamental change and transformation on all sides of social and cultural life, leading to a qualitative changes not only the public system, but also the emergence of innovative events in the spiritual system. In these circumstances, subject to quality guidelines and principles of the Reformation world, consciousness, values, science, intercultural communication, there is a change of scenarios, attitudes to technology and technology education system and knowledge-hull.

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In modern conditions the interaction of new media tools creates a media culture man who not only lives in the media environment, but also develops personally through it. By personality we mean a self-acting, endowed with the will and aspirations of the human individual, which "appears connected with other such human individuals and learn about their manner of treatment, the statements, the will and aspirations, meeting with their thoughts and views, opinions and takes some position with respect to their claims - pits, moods and values "[1], expressing their thoughts, opinions, judgments, as being the claims and rights, attitudes and evaluations.

At the heart of all these deep transformations is more increasing, almost defining role knowledge and information as play substrata of «information society». The mankind opened for itself and actively exploits a new resource – information. Information society puts forward on the arena new type of the power, at the heart of which activity – mastering by a new resource: information and knowledge. The password of the new power – intelligence as synthesis of knowledge, information and communications- is the strength of mind and fundamental sociocultural values. Information should become a material for knowledge, and then knowledge the maintenance of professionalism, intelligence of shots as bases both economic, and political, both social, and spiritual creativity.

In today's information-rich reality of new changes, which are significant science, innovation, education and information technology. The integration of science, innovation, education and information technology is based on the knowledge, fundamentally changing not only the social reality, but also qualitatively altering a person's attitude to the world, his world, the consciousness, values, and the role of social institutions in the cultural adaptation and socialization .

Among the many social institutions that are actively involved in the complex process of cultural adaptation and socialization, is the institution of higher education. Higher education in modern conditions of formation of a new infrastructure belongs to a complex role of acculturation and socialization in the formation of new ideological orientation and a system of spiritual values. In modern conditions, the system of higher education is becoming one of the leading cultural institutions in the complex process of acculturation rights in post-industrial society into a new world - a media culture.

One of the leading theoreticians of the modern media education, the British scientist and educator L. Masterman seven reasons to substantiate the relevance

of media education in the modern world:

- 1) a high level of consumption of media saturation of contemporary societies and the media;
- 2) the ideological importance of the media and their influence on the minds of the audience;
- 3) rapid growth in the number of media information, strengthening mechanisms for its management and distribution;
- 4) the penetration of the major media in the democratic process;
- 5) the increasing importance of visual communication and information in all areas;
- 6) the need for education of pupils / students with an orientation to meet future requirements;
- 7) the growing national and international processes of privatization of information [2].

For Kazakhstan, a particularly important stage of the program of modernization and innovative renewal of society is the improvement of educational policy, particularly in higher education. This problem stems from the fact that society requires not only innovative technology, modernized production, but also the appropriate professionals who could work in the contemporary social and cultural space, based on new knowledge and innovative outlook. Modern educational policy should be to prepare the educated, business, enterprising, competitive professionals. Over 20 years of independent development in Kazakhstan there were qualitative changes in education policy: UNT system was introduced, the public credit, grant support. All of these reforms in educational policy ultimately aimed at creating conditions for the formation of intellectual capital in the face with a specialist vocational education, with opportunities for cultural adaptation. In this process plays an important role not only knowledge-component, but also the spiritual and moral values, rational worldview. An important issue is the philosophical understanding of new theoretical and methodological problems of education, educational policy in the modernization of Kazakhstan's society, the challenges of globalization.

One of the important problems of the philosophical and methodological level, which seek to understand the scientists, philosophers on education policy is the task of combining the features of national culture and value aspects of the Western model of education. A very important component of this task is the translation of the principle of tolerance and solidarity through the educational program. Along with this problem is especially acute problem of preserving ethnic and cultural identity, which is very important for young people and in general for society. This problem is closely linked not only with educational policy as a social and cultural institution, fulfilling the role of cultural adaptation but also plays an important role in the cultural socialization of young people and cultural identity. Thus, in the broadcast of cultural values and patterns of cultural communication and social relations play an important role, such as cultural studies academic subjects, ethnic culture, world culture, the history of Kazakh culture, history of science in shaping the ideological orientation and world-attitude plays an important role philosophy, history of religion? Cognitive and educational value and function of these disciplines, knowledge-capital of these disciplines

allow young people to not only get acquainted with various cultural and ethnic communities, to develop an idea of a multicultural diversity of the peoples of our planet, but also expands the notions of the uniqueness of their own ethnic culture, forms of interest to national the origins, traditions, language [3].

Over the years the ongoing reform of higher education in Kazakhstan aimed at forming the basis for the creation of conditions respond to the challenges of globalization. In this regard, introduced new standards of education, changed the emphasis from training, transfer of a body of knowledge, experience, on the other a more active form in which the proportion of self-education has expanded considerably. And with it the task was carried out aimed at finding new and creative methods of «learning», related research tasks, new original productions tasks and involving students in projects with a high proportion of the implementation methods of solving problems in practice. This formulation of the new educational objectives actualized number of theoretical and methodological and educational issues. Among them is a philosophical reflection on the new educational priorities, value systems, world outlook, cognitive tasks and methodical teaching plan. There was a problem of understanding the new paradigm of education in the context of globalization and modernization.

For the first time in Kazakhstan, was introduced 3-stair continuous system of education (bachelor's, masters, doctoral PhD).

In the higher education system was introduced academic mobility of students. The first of the students who had been sent to foreign countries for the summer semester, there were undergraduates. Our first graduate students traveled to foreign countries for a period of training for 15 days, month, and then one more semester. Since last year, our university has introduced a new system - distance learning.

«Dasein» modern man, his daily practice - the practice of obtaining news, transfer of knowledge and experience with the media, the practice of recreation, entertainment, creativity, possible thanks to the media, the practice of communication - habitually associated with the media and media technology: personal computers, television, mobile phone, etc. on the right to scientists, "a type of culture and civilization, which is education, we believe, should play in the present and near future is closely linked to the dominant media sphere today, but because the philosophy of education, engaged in identifying the source of cultural values and fundamental worldview education and training, is destined to enter media culture in the region of its priority interests "[4].

II. CONCLUSION

The result is increased levels of ME media competence / literacy audiences. Media competence is multidimensional and requires a broader perspective, based on advanced knowledge of the structure. An essential element of human development of media education is to create it's own media production, that is, owning messages to their operational discussion of virtual discussions, debates with Internet users located in different cities and countries. Media Education as a factor of cultural socialization and personal development is manifested in the fact that Kazakhstan's youth change their

media preferences, choosing virtual forms of communication, Internet technology, creating their own media, thus, forming a new media space, setting the information space of their own moral criteria, its measure of responsibility.

III. SUMMARY

This article discusses the characteristics and place of the theoretical and methodological problems of education in the context of media culture in Kazakhstan, showing the influence of media education in the development of distance education in an information society. And also provides an analysis of cultural socialization and personal development of man in modern society, the scientific concepts related to information society scholars.

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